

READING DIMENSIONS AND READING PROFILE OF GRADE TWO LEARNERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 4

Pages: 425-439

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1870

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11400800

Manuscript Accepted: 05-01-2024

Reading Dimensions and Reading Profile of Grade Two Learners

Esnaira D. Tamburac,* Carlito A. Abarquez

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The reading skills and traits of second-graders in the public primary schools in the East II District were assessed in this study, and the learners' profiles were categorized as independent, instructional, or frustrated. A modified survey questionnaire was used to collect data in the first quarter of the School Year 2023–2024. A sample of 175 respondents was randomly selected from 12 different schools. Ordinal regression analysis was used to look at the effects of socio-demographic profiles and the connections between reading profiles and dimensions. The results showed conflicting patterns when the respondents' reading habits were compared to their sociodemographic profiles—p-values exceeding 0.05. The mother's reading habits, reading materials, and occupation did not significantly correlate with the reading profiles. None of these traits was statistically significantly associated with the probability of having a reading profile that fitted into the "frustration" category. On the other hand, the father's educational background showed a strong correlation. With a McFadden value, the pseudo-R² goodness was found to be moderate, indicating that the socio-demographic factors under consideration can account for a reasonable portion of the variation in the reading profile.

Keywords: *reading profiles, reading dimensions, second graders, reading habits*

Introduction

Reading is an interactive process in which readers construct a meaningful representation of a text using effective reading skills. Effective reading skills were considered significant skills that had received a special focus on students' reading comprehension proficiency. If one possesses good reading skills, then one will do better at school and grow productively. Thus, teachers need to guide students to become independent and effective in our fast-paced and fast-growing society. Another impact of having reading skills would encourage a thirst for knowledge. It developed critical thinking that would provide a wide range of information and learning.

In the current setting of the study of East II District public elementary schools, most Grade 2 teachers had noted that despite the reading remedial sessions, the number of weak readers continued to rise each year. As of June of this school year 2023, there were 52 Grade 2 learners enrolled, 34 of whom had been classified as frustrated readers based on the PHIL-IRI Pretest results conducted in June of this year (Phil-IRI Report, 2023).

Reading as a field of teaching was considered one of the most important areas of teaching if not the most important ever. It was said to be one of the most necessary academic skills as well. Besides, it was a major pillar upon which the teaching and learning process was built. Reading skills affected students' reading comprehension. This allowed readers to understand what they were reading. It also interpreted ideas and injected meaning to printed words through specific reading practices. Alyousef (2019) divulged that reading skills involved an interactive process between readers and texts that resulted in reading fluency. Readers interacted with texts as they tried to extract the meaning of the different types of knowledge such as linguistic or systemic knowledge (bottom-up processing) and schematic knowledge (top-down processing). Nevertheless, without adequate reading comprehension skills, students might struggle in many subject areas. Eventually, reading comprehension needed a specific reading skill that augmented students' interest and motivation.

According to Bateman (2021), reading skills as manifested by their learning style were considered the real core of the reading process and a big process around which all other processes were centered. Their reading practices allowed them to become more comprehensible in terms of interpretation and give deeper into what they read. These skills such as acquiring the correct meaning, analyzing the author's point of view, and applying what one learned from reading to real-life situations were what constituted reading analysis. Although, strong reading skills helped students do well in language arts and reading class was only the beginning. Students had to use reading skills in every single subject they ever study and in almost every aspect of life. It was so sad to note that students who struggled with reading comprehension might fall so far behind in school that they had limited opportunities as an adult.

Furthermore, Davis (2018) emphasized that reading was fundamental in getting knowledge as all the lessons and learning activities were mostly based on the power of comprehensive reading. Indeed, it was necessary to read comprehensively. In addition, reading comprehensively really affected a learner's education and his life as a whole. Learning in any lesson depended on the understanding of the learning instrument of that lesson. Thus, a learner who cannot read comprehensively finds it difficult for him/her to be successful in his or her lessons. Reading has the potential to help English language learners become better readers and make improvements in other aspects of their English skills. The more they read, the more they broaden their vocabulary and can express concepts accurately and effectively to others. Increasing their ability to communicate also helped make them better individuals.

Imbued with the above statement, this study was conducted to determine the reading skills, reading dimensions, and reading profile level of Grade 2 learners of East II District Schools in Iligan City Division. Specifically, this study sought to address the significant relationship between the reading skills, reading dimensions, and reading profile level of the respondents. Thus, results were used by

the English teachers to provide the best strategies for further developing the learner's reading skills and dimensions.

Research Questions

The major goal of this research determined the reading skills and reading dimensions of East II District of Public Elementary School Grade two learners to measure their reading profile level classified as frustration, instructional, and independent. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the reading dimensions of the respondents in terms of,
 - 1.1 literal;
 - 1.2 interpretive; and
 - 1.3 applied?
2. What is the reading profile level of the respondents classified as,
 - 2.1 frustrations;
 - 2.2 instructional; and
 - 2.3 independent?
3. What are the socio-demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of,
 - 3.1 parents' highest educational attainment;
 - 3.2 occupation;
 - 3.3 reading practices;
 - 3.4 reading materials preferences; and
 - 3.5 time spent in reading?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the reading dimensions and the reading profile of the respondents?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the reading dimensions of the respondents?
6. Which of the socio-demographic profiles and the reading dimensions of the respondents significantly predict their reading profile?
7. What SLAC session on teaching reading can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research methods that were used in the study. It also discusses the research design, research environment, respondents and sampling procedures, research instruments and their validity, and the statistical treatment of the data.

Research Design

The researcher utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. This descriptive study described the reading dimensions and reading profile level of the Grade 2 learners of East II District Public Elementary Schools. It is correlational because it would find out the specific relationship between the reading dimensions, and the reading profile level of the respondents classified as frustration, instructional, and independent of the respondents in the form of the assessment test.

Participants

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents. The respondents of the study were the Grade 2 learners of East II District Schools in Iligan City Division. The Grade 2 level was classified into twelve (12) elementary schools only of District II. These twelve (12) schools consisted of an average of 30 learners in each class who belonged to a homogenous group. To get the total number of respondents, a sample size with a 5 percent margin of error was used in the study. A total respondent of one hundred (175) were obtained. A simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>School</i>	<i>Total Population of Grade Two Learners</i>	<i>Sample Respondents</i>
Hinaplanon Elementary School	58	29
Tubaran Elementary School	48	24
Mandulog Elementary School	43	22
Lanipao Elementary School	30	15
Dulag Elementary School	26	13
Kalilangan Elementary School	24	12
Upper Pigsoutan Elementary School	20	10
Pirandangan Elementary School	18	9
Anugod Elementary School	24	12
Unayan Elementary School	20	10
Tamanan Elementary School	22	11
Sapot Elementary School	16	8
Total	350	175

Instruments

The instrument used in this study was adapted from different researchers. Thus, these instruments are already tested and validated. In measuring the reading dimension achievement of the students, this study utilized the instrument of the Department of Education, Philippine – Informal Reading Inventory Group Screening Test (Phil-IRI-GST, 2018). This instrument is intended to measure and determine the level of reading profile comprehension performance of the students. Data that were gathered from the instrument were used to make or design and modify a large group of students into a small cluster or individualized to cater to the needs and deficiencies of the students. The Phil-IRI is not the only evaluation or assessment instrument that predicts the full reading achievements of the students. It only gives a rough calculation of the students' capacities and it can be used together with the other reading evaluation instrument that is valid. The data also served as a basis or guide in making a plan and designing/redesigning reading intervention programs in the educational institution to improve or raise the students' reading performance.

Moreover, the questionnaire was composed of two parts wherein the first part determined the learner's socio-demographic profile: parents' highest educational attainment, occupation, reading practices, reading materials preferences, and reading time spent in reading. The second part focused on the students' reading dimensions and profiles. The researcher presented the questionnaire to the panel of experts and presented it to the adviser for correction, enrichment, and finalization. Thereafter, the questionnaire was restructured as to the comments to be provided by the adviser.

The experts examined the instrument for comprehensiveness and correct the construction of the content of the questionnaire to ensure its validity. Statements in Part II of the instrument were taken from Cain, Katada, and Mascardo (2019) but were modified as to construction to address the problem of the study, hence validity testing need not be conducted, but they were still shown to experts for validation.

Procedure

With the recommendation of the panel members to conduct the study, the researcher initially requested an endorsement from the OIC of the Graduate School of St. Peter's College to gather the needed data. After the endorsement was sought, the researcher communicated to the Principal of the participating school by submitting a permission letter/consent letter to conduct a study for this research to be formal.

Informed consent was sent to the respondents days before the actual data gathering. The consent aimed to inform the respondents on the context, purpose, advantages, and disadvantages of participating in the study. Upon distributing the questionnaires, a hard copy was taken back from the respondents. Only those respondents who affixed their signatures on the informed consent form were given questionnaires to answer. This signified their voluntary participation in the study. The respondents were given enough to answer the questionnaires.

The researcher together with the select master teachers was asked and requested to administer the instrument to the respondents to collect data. The respondents were provided ample time to answer the questionnaires, after which these were retrieved. Responses were tabulated, collated, and were readied for statistical treatment.

Statistical Treatment

The data were tabulated and interpreted to acquire the actual information needed. The following statistical tools were employed to answer the different problems presented:

For problems 1, and 2, Frequency and Percentage, Mean and Standard deviation were used to determine the learners' reading dimensions and reading profile level.

For problem 3, Frequency and Percentage were used in determining the profile of the respondents in terms of parents' highest educational attainment, occupation, reading practices, reading materials preferences, and time spent in reading.

For problems 4, 5, and 6, Ordinal regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between the learners' reading profile and reading dimensions, and the relationship between socio-demographic profile and reading dimensions and reading profile, and to test if the predictors significantly affected the learners' reading profile level.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data in relevance to the reading dimension. For better analysis and interpretation, these data are presented in tabular and graphical forms. For authentic discussions, this chapter employs related literature and studies.

Problem 1: What are the reading dimensions of the respondents in terms of literal, interpretive, and applied?

Table 2 presents the literal reading dimensions among the respondents, shedding light on their performance across various score ranges. Notably, there was a complete absence of respondents falling within the "Outstanding" range (9-10), indicating a collective challenge in achieving the highest level of literal comprehension. The most substantial portion of the respondents, 37.7%, fell into the "Below Average" category (3-4), revealing a noteworthy deficiency in literal reading skills within the sample.

Table 2. Reading Dimensions of the Respondents in Terms of Literal

Actual Score Range	Verbal Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
9-10	Outstanding	0	0.0
7-8	Very Good	11	6.3
5-6	Average	36	20.6
3-4	Below Average	66	37.7
0-2	Weak	62	35.4
Total		175	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 3.33 (1.83)

Additionally, 35.4% of respondents were classified as "Weak" (0-2), further emphasizing a significant proportion struggling in this aspect. Conversely, 6.3% and 20.6% of respondents demonstrated "Very Good" and "Average" literal reading skills, respectively, suggesting a smaller yet notable segment with satisfactory performance. The mean score of 3.33 with a standard deviation of 1.83 provided a central tendency and dispersion measure, indicating the overall average performance and the extent of variability within the group. These results underscored the urgency of targeted interventions and literacy programs to address the prevailing weaknesses in literal reading comprehension.

The data implied that most of the pupils were still at the literal level of reading comprehension. The literal level implied recognition of what was simply, directly, and explicitly stated in the textual message. It is the ability to obtain a low-level type of understanding by using only information explicitly stated in the text. In this level, the answer to literal questions simply demanded that the reader recall what the text says, word recognition was subsumed here (Gillaco, 2019). Since most of them were excellent, they still needed more reading improvement for the next level of reading comprehension skills.

Table 3. Reading Dimensions of the Respondents in Terms of Interpretative

Actual Score	Verbal Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
5	Outstanding	0	0.0
4	Very Good	5	2.9
3	Average	32	18.3
2	Below Average	63	36.0
0-1	Weak	75	42.9
Total		175	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 1.66 (1.02)

Table 3 shows the interpretative reading dimensions of the respondents. Several respondents fell into the "Weak" category (0-1) with a substantial percentage of 42.9%, indicating a significant challenge in mastering the interpretative aspect of reading. Moreover, 36.0% of respondents were classified as "Below Average" (2), further emphasizing a prevalent struggle in this dimension.

On the positive side, 2.9% and 18.3% of respondents demonstrated "Very Good" (4) and "Average" (3) interpretative reading skills, respectively, suggesting a smaller but notable segment with satisfactory performance. The mean score of 1.66 with a standard deviation of 1.02 provided insight into the central tendency and dispersion of scores, indicating an overall below-average performance with a relatively low level of variability.

These results underscored the need for targeted interventions and literacy programs to enhance interpretative reading skills among the majority of the respondents. The findings suggested that addressing weaknesses in interpretative reading could significantly contribute to overall reading comprehension improvement, emphasizing the importance of tailored strategies and interventions to uplift these skills.

Meanwhile, reading necessitated a high level of comprehension. Reading between the lines or interpretative reading meant containing information and making inferences and comprehending them, as well as answering questions on knowledge such as who, what, where, and when. The process of applying or reading beyond the lines to express opinions and generate ideas entailed application, analysis, and synthesis (Alcantara et al., 2018). It implied that most of the pupils had responded and given judgments on the texts they had read because according to Gillaco (2019), that the interpretative level went beyond the direct and explicit statement. It also demanded higher thinking because these concerns were not directly stated in the text but were suggested or implied. Reading at this stage was also called reading between the lines combining the information with inferred meaning.

Table 4. Reading Dimensions of the Respondents in Terms of Applied

Actual Score	Verbal Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
5	Outstanding	1	0.6
4	Very Good	2	1.1
3	Average	21	12.0
2	Below Average	53	30.3
0-1	Weak	98	56.0
Total		175	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 1.43 (.98)

Table 4 outlines the distribution of scores among respondents concerning the applied reading dimension, providing insights into their performance and corresponding verbal descriptions. Remarkably, only a marginal percentage, 0.6%, achieved an "Outstanding" score of 5, indicating a rare mastery of applied reading skills within the sample. The majority of respondents, constituting 56.0%, fell into the "Weak" category (0-1), emphasizing a significant challenge in mastering applied reading.

Additionally, 30.3% of respondents were classified as "Below Average" (2), indicating a clear struggle in this dimension. On a positive note, 1.1% and 12.0% of respondents demonstrated "Very Good" (4) and "Average" (3) applied reading skills, respectively, suggesting a smaller yet appreciable segment with satisfactory performance. The mean score of 1.43 with a standard deviation of 0.98 suggested an overall below-average performance with a moderate level of variability. These results underscored a pressing need for targeted interventions and literacy programs to enhance applied reading skills among the majority of the respondents.

The data also implied that the learners were able to evaluate the text. The applied level was also called reading beyond the lines. It involved the making of a personal judgment on the text by the reader. It required a response indicating that an evaluative judgment had been made. It required experience, especially on the part of giving judgment. It needed a response indicating that an evaluative judgment had been made. It showed experience especially on the part of giving judgment (Gillaco, 2019).

Table 5. *Reading Dimensions of the Respondents (Total Measure)*

<i>Actual Score Range</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
17-20	Outstanding	0	0.0
12-16	Very Good	3	1.7
8-11	Average	64	36.6
4-7	Below Average	78	44.6
0-3	Weak	30	17.1
Total		175	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 6.42 (2.62)

Table 5 consolidates the total reading scores for the respondents, encompassing all three dimensions (Literal, Interpretative, and Applied). The scores were categorized into five ranges, each associated with a verbal description.

As could be seen in the result, none of the respondents achieved an "Outstanding" total score in the 17-20 range, signaling a collective challenge in reaching the highest level of reading comprehension across all dimensions. Several of the respondents, comprising 44.6%, fell into the "Below Average" category (4-7), indicating a significant deficiency in the overall reading skills of the surveyed population.

Furthermore, 36.6% of respondents were classified as "Average" (8-11), suggesting a substantial portion with moderate overall reading proficiency. On a positive note, 1.7% of respondents demonstrated "Very Good" (12-16) total reading skills, indicating a smaller but noteworthy segment with commendable performance. The mean total score of 6.42 with a standard deviation of 2.62 provided an average performance indicator and the extent of variability within the group. These results emphasized the need for comprehensive interventions targeting all aspects of reading—literal, interpretative, and applied—to improve overall reading comprehension.

According to Krashen (1987), children read well or poorly for certain definite causes. A teacher must be able to make an analysis of each case and determine the points of strength or weakness before he can intelligently give help. In addition, factors that control the reading process that influence the acquisition of reading ability may be grouped into intrinsic and extrinsic.

Problem 2: What is the reading profile level of the respondents classified as frustrations, instructional, and independent?

Table 6. *Reading Profile Level of the Respondents*

<i>Reading Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Frustration	131	74.9
Instructional	44	25.1
Independent	0	0.0
Total	175	100.0

Table 6 depicts the reading profile levels of the respondents, categorizing them into three distinct classifications: Frustration, Instructional, and Independent. The overwhelming majority of respondents, constituting 74.9%, fell within the "Frustration" category, indicating that a significant portion of the respondents encountered challenges and struggles in their current reading proficiency.

Conversely, 25.1% of respondents were classified as "Instructional," suggesting that a smaller but notable segment possessed reading skills at a level where they could benefit from instructional support. Interestingly, no respondents were categorized as "Independent," signaling a complete absence of individuals who could comfortably navigate and comprehend texts without assistance.

These findings underscored the pressing need for targeted interventions and literacy programs to address the widespread challenges in reading proficiency among the surveyed population. The absence of individuals in the "Independent" category suggested a gap in self-sufficiency in reading, highlighting the importance of implementing strategies to empower individuals to read autonomously.

One of the recent studies concluded that effective vocabulary instruction for comprehension would require teachers to devote absurdly large amounts of time and energy to vocabulary instruction. It should cover every word in the selection that students might not know,

with rich, intensive instruction that tied the words in with background knowledge. They should engage the students actively in meaningful processing and doing all of these 10 or more times per word (Agate, 2019).

Problem 3: What are the socio-demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of parents' highest educational attainment, occupation, reading practices, reading materials preferences, and time spent in reading?

Table 7. *Parents' Educational Attainment of the Respondents*

Educational Attainment	Mother		Father	
	F	%	F	%
College Graduate	29	16.6	23	13.1
College Level	50	28.6	57	32.6
High School Graduate	64	36.6	64	36.6
Elementary Graduate	18	10.3	20	11.4
Elementary Level	14	8.0	11	6.3
Total	175	100.0	175	100.0

Table 7 provides insight into the educational attainment of the respondent's parents, disaggregated by mothers and fathers. The educational backgrounds were categorized into five levels: College Graduate, College Level, High School Graduate, Elementary Graduate, and Elementary Level.

Notably, nearly 1/3 of mothers (36.6%) and fathers (36.6%) had attained a High School diploma, indicating a prevalent educational level among the parents in the sample data. Additionally, a significant portion of mothers (28.6%) and fathers (32.6%) had completed some college units but had not graduated, reflecting a noteworthy presence of individuals with college-level education. College graduates among mothers and fathers represented 16.6% and 13.1%, respectively, highlighting a minority with higher educational achievements.

Moreover, a smaller proportion of parents had educational backgrounds at the Elementary Level and Elementary Graduate levels. These findings underscored the diverse educational backgrounds within the respondents' families, suggesting a need for targeted interventions that considered the varying levels of parental education. The educational context of the home was crucial for understanding the support systems available to students, and tailoring literacy programs to accommodate this diversity might contribute to more effective interventions.

Furthermore, parents' educational attainment was considered as one of the factors affecting learner's reading comprehension skills. Mare (2020) said that those children with families whose parents have less education tend to systematically perform worse than those children whose parents attained high education.

Table 8. *Parents' Occupation of the Respondents*

Occupation	Mother		Father	
	F	%	F	%
Government Employee	12	6.9	14	8.0
Self-employed	16	9.1	9	5.1
Overseas Filipino Worker	133	76.0	128	73.1
Business	14	8.0	24	13.7
Total	175	100.0	175	100.0

Table 8 displays the occupational distribution of the respondents' parents, distinguishing between mothers and fathers. Clearly, a significant majority of both mothers (76.0%) and fathers (73.1%) were classified as Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs), indicating a prevalent trend of parents working abroad for employment opportunities. This finding highlighted the potential impact of parental absence due to overseas employment on the support and guidance available to the respondents.

Government employment was represented by 6.9% of mothers and 8.0% of fathers, suggesting a minority within the sample holding public sector positions. Self-employed individuals constituted 9.1% of mothers and 5.1% of fathers, indicating a smaller proportion engaged in entrepreneurial activities. The Business category was represented by 8.0% of mothers and 13.7% of fathers.

These occupational profiles provided crucial contextual information for understanding the socioeconomic dynamics within the families of the respondents. The high prevalence of Overseas Filipino Workers suggested a potential need for support structures and interventions that considered the unique challenges faced by families with parents working abroad.

It was shown in the table that the majority of respondents' parents were both OFWs. Some mothers were housewives but chose the option – “self-employed” as an occupation. In support of this, Reyes and Verano (as cited by Larayos & Malawani, 2019) in the Philippine setting, it was evident that mothers were expected to stay at home to nurse and guide the children's character, formation, growth, and development while the husband works as OFW.

Meanwhile, respondents' fathers were also capable of landing a decent job to provide and sustain the family's needs. As a result, children most likely look up to their mothers' help, especially to school or home work.

Table 9. Reading Materials Available at Home

<i>Reading Materials</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
None	1	0.6
Story Books	52	29.7
Encyclopaedias	94	53.7
Dictionaries	22	12.6
Journals	5	2.9
Magazines	1	0.6
Newspapers	0	0.0
Educational Books	0	0.0
Electronic Books	0	0.0
Total	175	100.0

Table 9 provides details into the availability of various reading materials at the respondents' homes, offering a glimpse into the literary environment within their households. The result showed a vast majority of respondents, 53.7%, had access to encyclopedias, indicating a prevalence of comprehensive informational resources within their homes. Storybooks were also quite common, with 29.7% of respondents reporting their availability, suggesting a presence of imaginative and narrative literature. Dictionaries, representing 12.6%, further contributed to the linguistic resources available. Journals and magazines were less prevalent, with 2.9% and 0.6% respectively, indicating a relatively lower frequency of these materials in the surveyed households. Surprisingly, no respondents reported having newspapers, educational books, or electronic books at home.

The findings shed light on the diversity and distribution of reading materials within the respondents' homes. The high prevalence of encyclopedias suggested a focus on factual and informative content, potentially contributing to the development of knowledge and reference skills. However, the limited availability of newspapers, educational books, and electronic books might suggest areas for improvement in terms of exposing respondents to current affairs, specialized educational content, and digital reading resources.

Thus, the information shown above implied that home provided the foundation for early literacy. It also played a prominent role in the development of children's positive attitudes, self-concepts, and reading skills. This was accomplished through access to reading resources, exposure to model reading behavior, and participation in early literacy activities that provided them with the skills for formal education (Mullis et al., 2019). As quoted in Wu (2020), showed a higher frequency of reading backwardness in the lower socio-economic group and showed that the availability of reading materials at home was a factor that could contribute to the reading of the pupils.

Table 10. Reading Practices of the Respondents

<i>Reading Practices</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. How often do your parents guide and encourage you to read more?	2.15	.61	Seldom
2. How often do your parents visit/consult your teachers?	2.04	.59	Seldom
3. How often do your parents attend your school gatherings?	2.10	.64	Seldom
Total Measure	2.10	.48	Seldom

Note: 1.001-1.49 Never 2.50-3.00 Always 1.50-2.49 Seldom

Table 10 provides an overview of the reading practices of the respondents, including the frequency of parental guidance and involvement in various aspects related to their education. In terms of parental encouragement to read more, the respondents reported a mean score of 2.15 with a standard deviation of 0.61, indicating that, on average, parental guidance and encouragement to read more occur "Seldom." Similarly, the mean scores for the frequency of parents visiting or consulting teachers (2.04, SD = 0.59) and attending school gatherings (2.10, SD = 0.64) also suggested that these practices were perceived as occurring "Seldom" by the respondents.

The total measure, combining these three aspects of parental involvement, yielded a mean score of 2.10 with a standard deviation of 0.48, reaffirming an overall perception of these practices as happening "Seldom."

These findings underscored a consistent pattern of limited parental involvement in the educational aspects of the respondents' lives. The "Seldom" description suggested a potential area for improvement in terms of enhancing parental engagement in activities related to reading and overall school participation. These insights could guide educators and policymakers in developing strategies to encourage and facilitate increased parental involvement, fostering a more supportive educational environment for the respondents.

The result regarding the guidance and encouragements implied that a supportive home environment began with positive parental attitudes toward reading and a high value placed on literacy. As manifested by Baker and Scher as cited by Dingco and Sumile (2019) children whose parents had positive beliefs about reading for pleasure had higher motivation as readers.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the reading dimensions and the reading profile of the respondents?

Table 11 presents the relationship between the reading dimensions (Literal, Interpretative, Applied) and the reading profile of the respondents, as indicated by the estimates, standard errors, Wald statistics, p-values, and remarks.

For the Literal reading dimension, the estimate was 4.507 with a standard error of 1.065 and a Wald statistic of 17.911, resulting in a

highly significant p-value of .000. Similarly, for the Interpretative reading dimension, the estimate was 4.388 with a standard error of 1.080 and a Wald statistic of 16.499, also yielding a highly significant p-value of .000. For the Applied reading dimension, the estimate was 4.222 with a standard error of 1.224 and a Wald statistic of 11.896, with a significant p-value of .001.

Table 11. Relationships Between the Reading Dimensions and the Reading Profile of the Respondents

Reading Dimensions	Estimate	S. E.	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Literal	4.507	1.065	17.911***	.000	Significant
Interpretative	4.388	1.080	16.499***	.000	Significant
Applied	4.222	1.224	11.896***	.001	Significant

The threshold for the reading profile being frustration indicated that these relationships were assessed concerning the respondents' reading profiles, particularly the likelihood of falling into the "Frustration" category. The McFadden R2 value was .868, indicating a high level of pseudo-R2 goodness of fit for the model. The "Significant" remarks for each reading dimension suggested that there was a statistically significant relationship between each dimension (Literal, Interpretative, Applied) and the likelihood of the respondents falling into the "Frustration" category in their reading profile.

This implied that as the scores in each reading dimension increased, there was a corresponding decrease in the likelihood of being categorized as "Frustration." These findings were crucial for educators and policymakers, emphasizing the importance of addressing specific reading dimensions to potentially alleviate frustrations and challenges in overall reading proficiency among the surveyed population.

As manifested by Anderson et al. (2019) the ultimate goal of reading instruction was comprehension then, the learners were able to cope with the ultimate goal because as gleaned on the data presented. Learners were considered excellent at the literal level and performed well in interpretive, and applied levels. Perhaps, the learners were expected to be active, purposeful readers whose brains were always working and thinking while they read.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the reading dimensions of the respondents?

Table 12. Relationships Between the Socio-Demographic Profile and the Reading Profile of the Respondents

Reading Dimensions	Estimate	S. E.	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Reading Practices	.447	.349	1.637	.201	Not significant
Mother Education					
College Graduate	-.268	.972	.076	.783	Not significant
College Level	-.166	.907	.034	.855	Not significant
High School Graduate	.517	.879	.345	.557	Not significant
Elementary Graduate	.804	.920	.764	.382	Not significant
Elementary Level	Ref	--	--	--	--
Father Education					
College Graduate	-1.788	1.201	2.215	.137	Not significant
College Level	-1.134	1.110	1.044	.307	Not significant
High School Graduate	-.884	1.100	.646	.421	Not significant
Elementary Graduate	-.378	1.082	.122	.727	Not significant
Elementary Level	Ref	--	--	--	--
Mother Occupation					
Government Employee	1.685	1.149	2.150	.143	Not significant
Self-employed	-.448	.807	.307	.579	Not significant
Overseas Filipino Worker	-.745	.607	1.509	.219	Not significant
Business	Ref	--	--	--	--
Father Occupation					
Government Employee	-1.425	.821	3.017	.082	Not significant
Self-employed	.017	.929	.000	.985	Not significant
Overseas Filipino Worker	-.180	.546	.108	.742	Not significant
Business	Ref	--	--	--	--
Reading Materials					
Story Books	-1.354	1.186	1.304	.254	Not significant
Encyclopaedias	-.767	1.179	.422	.516	Not significant
Dictionaries	-1.709	1.266	1.822	.177	Not significant
Journals	Ref	--	--	--	--

Note: Threshold [reading dimension = Weak] Threshold [reading dimension=Below Average]
McFadden R2 = .107 ***significant at .001 level

Table 12 presents the relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the reading profile of the respondents, including estimates, standard errors, Wald statistics, p-values, and remarks.

For the Reading Practices, Mother Education, Father Education, Mother Occupation, Father Occupation, and Reading Materials, the estimates, standard errors, and Wald statistics were provided. The p-values and remarks indicated whether the relationship was statistically significant.

Reading Practices showed a not significant relationship (p-value = .201), suggesting that how often parents guide and encourage reading was not significantly associated with the respondents' reading profile. Similarly, Mother Education, Father Education, Mother Occupation, Father Occupation, and Reading Materials all showed no significant relationships with the reading profile of the respondents. The thresholds for reading dimensions being "Weak" or "Below Average" indicated that these relationships were assessed concerning the likelihood of the respondents falling into these specific reading categories. The McFadden R2 value was .107, suggesting a low level of pseudo-R2 goodness of fit for the model.

Overall, the non-significant relationships in this result implied that, based on the socio-demographic factors considered, there was no statistically significant association with the likelihood of the respondents falling into specific reading profile categories. These findings highlighted the complexity of factors influencing reading profiles, and additional variables or a more nuanced analysis may be needed to better understand the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and reading proficiency among the surveyed population.

Furthermore, it was still important for us to note that home involvement was encouraged to improve the reading comprehension skills of the learner. Mullis et al. (2019) emphasized that home provided the foundation for early literacy, and played a prominent role in the development of children's positive attitudes, self-concepts, and reading skills. It was accomplished through access to reading resources, exposure to reading behavior, and participation in early literacy activities that provided them with the skills for formal education.

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the reading profile of the respondents?

Table 13. Relationships Between the Socio-Demographic Profile and the Reading Profile of the Respondents

Reading Dimensions	Estimate	S. E.	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Reading Practices	-.060	.459	.017	.896	Not significant
Mother Education					
College Graduate	.815	1.195	.465	.495	Not significant
College Level	.467	1.087	.185	.667	Not significant
High School Graduate	.602	1.018	.350	.554	Not significant
Elementary Graduate	1.251	1.092	1.313	.252	Not significant
Elementary Level	Ref	--	--	--	--
Father Education					
College Graduate	-5.517	1.789	9.512**	.002	Significant
College Level	-3.064	1.364	5.045*	.025	Significant
High School Graduate	-3.617	1.347	7.207**	.007	Significant
Elementary Graduate	-1.675	1.221	1.884	.170	Not significant
Elementary Level	Ref	--	--	--	--
Mother Occupation					
Government Employee	-1.068	1.187	.810	.368	Not significant
Self-employed	-1.673	1.173	2.034	.154	Not significant
Overseas Filipino Worker	-.763	.688	1.231	.267	Not significant
Business	Ref	--	--	--	--
Father Occupation					
Government Employee	-.545	.961	.321	.571	Not significant
Self-employed	-1.623	1.399	1.345	.246	Not significant
Overseas Filipino Worker	.085	.675	.016	.900	Not significant
Business	Ref	--	--	--	--
Reading Materials					
Story Books	-.813	.1432	.323	.570	Not significant
Encyclopaedias	-1.522	1.431	1.132	.287	Not significant
Dictionaries	-1.933	1.542	1.572	.210	Not significant
Journals	Ref	--	--	--	--

Note: Threshold [reading profile = frustration] McFadden R2 = .202 **significant at .001 level *significant at .05 level

Table 13 outlines the relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the reading profile of the respondents, presenting estimates, standard errors, Wald statistics, p-values, and remarks.

In terms of reading practices, mother education, mother occupation, and reading materials, the estimates indicated no significant relationships with the respondents' reading profiles. For these variables, the p-values were above the threshold of significance (p > .05), implying that these factors did not have a statistically significant association with the likelihood of falling into the "frustration" reading profile.

However, the father education variable showed a statistically significant relationship with the reading profile. The estimates for college graduate, college-level, and high-school-graduate fathers were negative, suggesting a decreasing likelihood of being in the “Frustration” reading profile category as the father’s education level increases. The p-values for these estimates were below the .05 threshold, indicating statistical significance.

The McFadden R2 value of .202 suggested a moderate level of pseudo-R2 goodness of fit for the model, indicating that the considered socio-demographic factors explained a reasonable proportion of the variation in the reading profile. In summary, this result emphasized that, among the socio-demographic factors considered, the father’s education level emerged as a significant predictor of the respondents’ reading profile. This insight was valuable for educators and policymakers, suggesting that interventions targeting parental education, particularly fathers, may have a meaningful impact on improving reading proficiency and mitigating frustration among the surveyed population.

McNamara (2019) contended that Reading Thinking "(RT) was a well-validated approach to improve students` comprehension and self-monitoring skills through an apprenticeship model of learning" (p. 31). He asserted that "the teacher and students engaged in an instructional dialogue about the text, constructing their understanding of the text as they applied several strategies: predicting, questioning, summarizing, and clarifying" (p.38). Further, with active reading tasks, readers were encouraged to voice their own opinions about the text and discuss those opinions with other students and the teacher.

Problem 7: What SLAC session on teaching reading can be designed based on the findings of the study?

This SLAC session, “Enhancing Reading Instruction,” is designed to empower educators with targeted strategies for improving student reading proficiency. The rationale behind this session lies in the comprehensive analysis of students’ reading profiles and socio-demographic factors, as evidenced in Tables 11, 12, and 13. By examining the relationships between reading dimensions and profiles, as well as socio-demographic influences, educators gain insights into the specific challenges their students face. The session aims to foster collaborative discussions on effective reading practices and instructional interventions tailored to diverse student needs. By leveraging the collective expertise within the SLAC, educators can develop actionable plans for enhancing reading instruction, ensuring a more inclusive and impactful approach that addresses the unique dynamics present in their classrooms. Through this collaborative initiative, the SLAC session seeks to empower educators with the tools and knowledge needed to make a meaningful impact on students’ reading abilities, ultimately fostering a more literate and engaged learning community.

Title: Enhancing Reading Instruction: A Collaborative Approach to Addressing Student Profiles

<i>Components</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>
Introduction	Understand the importance of effective reading instruction. – Recognize the role of SLAC in professional development. Identify common challenges in students’ reading profiles.	Brief presentation on the impact of reading instruction. – Discuss SLAC’s purpose and collaborative nature.	Participants comprehend the significance of teaching reading and understand SLAC’s role.
Review of Reading Profiles	– Analyze the relationship between reading dimensions and profiles.	Discuss implications for instructional planning.	Participants gain insights into factors influencing reading profiles and recognize the need for tailored instruction.
Socio-Demographic Analysis	Examine the influence of socio-demographic factors on reading profiles. – Identify potential areas for intervention.	Discuss how to address identified areas in teaching.	Participants recognize the impact of socio-demographic factors on reading and brainstorm strategies for targeted instruction.
Effective Reading Practices	Explore strategies for encouraging and guiding students’ reading. – Understand the role of parental involvement.	Share effective reading practices. – Discuss how to enhance parent-teacher collaboration.	Participants acquire a toolkit of effective reading practices and collaborative strategies with parents.
Planning Instructional Interventions	Develop strategies to address weaknesses in reading dimensions. – Formulate plans for differentiated instruction.	Brainstorm instructional interventions based on reading dimensions. – Collaborative discussion on tailoring instruction to diverse needs.	Participants create actionable plans for addressing specific reading challenges within their classrooms.
Reflection and Feedback	Reflect on key takeaways from the session. – Provide constructive feedback for improvement.	Individual and group reflection on insights gained. – Open forum for feedback and suggestions.	Participants leave with a clear understanding of the session’s content and provide feedback for continuous improvement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: The study revealed intricate patterns in the respondents' reading abilities. The absence of top-tier scores in literal reading and the prevalence of subpar ratings suggested underlying complexities beyond standard grading metrics. This prompted a reevaluation of teaching methodologies to foster a more profound and comprehensive grasp of the text, urging educators to explore alternative approaches.

Within the reading profiles, the dominance of the "Frustration" category indicates a widespread struggle that extended beyond conventional proficiency levels. The lack of "Independent" categorizations suggested a potential misalignment between traditional teaching methods and the development of self-reliant readers. This prompted a reflection on how educational systems could adapt to equip students with the skills and confidence for autonomous engagement with texts, moving beyond comprehension to critical analysis and synthesis.

While socio-demographic factors exhibited limited direct impact on reading profiles, the significance of father education introduced an intriguing aspect. The negative estimates suggested a subtle influence of paternal educational levels, prompting further exploration into the dynamics of parental involvement in creating a conducive reading environment. This underscored the need for more profound engagement strategies that surpassed surface-level involvement, potentially uncovering hidden potentials in students' literacy development.

In essence, these findings challenged educators and policymakers to reassess conventional literacy approaches. It called for a holistic strategy that not only addresses immediate challenges in literal, interpretative, and applied dimensions but also nurtured independent critical thinking. The nuanced influence of father education invited a broader exploration of the intricate interplay between familial dynamics and educational outcomes, encouraging educators to reconsider their methods in creating a richer and more empowering learning environment.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are hereby suggested: (1) For school administrators, the findings underscore the importance of implementing targeted interventions to address the identified challenges in students' reading abilities. These interventions could involve professional development opportunities for teachers, incorporating innovative teaching methods, and investing in resources that promote a holistic approach to literacy. Additionally, creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment that considers individual differences in learning styles and needs can contribute to improved overall literacy outcomes. (2) Curriculum designers should consider the integration of diverse and engaging reading materials that cater to various interests and reading levels. A flexible curriculum that allows for personalized learning experiences can help address the diverse literacy needs observed among the respondents. Furthermore, incorporating literacy skills development across subject areas can reinforce and enhance overall reading proficiency. (3) Teachers can benefit from professional development programs that focus on effective strategies for literacy instruction, including differentiated instruction and tailored approaches for literal, interpretative, and applied dimensions. Regular assessments and feedback mechanisms can inform instructional adjustments, ensuring a responsive and dynamic teaching environment. Encouraging a collaborative culture among educators to share best practices and insights can also contribute to a more effective and supportive teaching community. (4) For learners, fostering a proactive and self-directed approach to reading is crucial. Encouraging independent reading habits, self-assessment, and setting personalized literacy goals can empower students to take ownership of their learning journey. Providing access to a diverse range of reading materials aligned with individual interests and abilities can further enhance intrinsic motivation and engagement. (5) Finally, future researchers should build upon this study by delving into the effectiveness of specific literacy interventions and exploring the long-term impact of socio-demographic factors on reading proficiency. Investigating the role of parental involvement, particularly fathers, in shaping literacy outcomes can provide deeper insights into the dynamics of familial influence on educational achievement.

References

- Aarnoutse, R., & Leeuwe, Y. (2018). *Reading first and beyond: The complete guide for teachers and literacy coaches*. Corwin Press.
- Abalos, G. (2015). Parental involvement and children's school achievement. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*.
- Adler, H. (2019). Home involvement in schooling school mental health project. Dept. of Psychology. Center for Mental Health in Schools.
- Agate, B. (2019). Prediction of elementary student reading achievement from specific home environment variables. *Reading Improvement*, 27(3), 173-178.
- Alauya, J. & Macabuntal, N. (2011). Reading comprehension level of grade six pupils: Basis for an action plan. Unpublished Graduate Thesis, MSU-IIT.
- Albarico, G. (2019). Give books to children in the Philippines by the center for art. *New Ventures & Sustainable Development (CANVAS)*.
- Alcantara, D., Santos, T., Ramos, R., & Zamora, L. (2018). Reading rate and comprehension as a function versus traditional

presentation mode: A preliminary study. *Journal of Education Technology*, 22, 1–12.

Alico, E. (2018). The use of the contextualized module in teaching Biology: Basis for teachers' training. Master's thesis, Capitol University, Cagayan de Oro City.

Allington, C., (2019). Seven strategies to teach student's reading comprehension. Rocketorg reading. <http://www.readingrockets.org>.

Almutari, A. (2018). Strategy intervention to enhance reading comprehension of 15-year-old students in Mexico. https://file:///c:/users/user/Desktop/phd_thesis.

Alyousef, F. A. (2019). The relationship of parental involvement and reading achievement of 9th-grade students. Walden: Walden University Scholarworks.

Anderson, S.A. (2018). How parental involvement makes a difference in reading achievement. www.freepatentsonline.com. www.freepatentsonline.com/article/Reading-Improvement/63500391.html.

Aranton, A.N. (2019). An assessment of the reading ability of the elementary pupils at St.Peters College. M.A.thesis .St.Peters College Iligan City.

Ausubel, T. (2018). Cognitive learning theory: Meaningful learning theory, subsumption theory and motivational theory. <http://cimprelims.wikia.com/wiki/>.

Baker, A. (2019). Characteristics of children who are unresponsive to early reading literacy intervention. *Academia*, 300-316.

Bateman, M. (2021). Reading the master's house: New knowledge movements and the emergence of academic disciplines. *Digital Commons @ RIC*, 401-451.

Bell, P.R., & Perfetti, T.M. (2018). Maternal reading and teaching patterns: Associations with school readiness in low-income African American families. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 41(1), 68-89.

Best, J.W. (2018). *Research in education*. Prentice Hall, USA.

Betty, S. (2019). Metacognitive process and reading comprehension. <https://www.journalwriting/publication/educ.pdf>.4132.

Biemiller, S. (2018). Reading comprehension strategy instruction and attribution retraining for secondary students with disabilities. *Dissertation Abstracts: Humanities and Social Sciences* 68 (3-A): dx.sagepub.com/content/44.

Block, F., & Presley, G. (2018). *Reciprocal teaching at improving reading comprehension*. Newark, DE: International Reading Association.

Bond, A. (2019). The relationship between reading comprehension and parent support. Doctoral Dissertation. Walden University. <http://search.proquest.com/docview/902746076/AC714B71318F4BA4PQ>.

Brint, M. (2021). The structural relationship of reading attitude, reading comprehension, and academic achievement. *International J. Soc.Scie. & Education*.

Bromley, C. (2019). Toward a multicomponent model of interest and L2 reading. Sources of interest perceived situational interest, and comprehension. *Reading in Foreign Language*.

Brown, H. D. (2018). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy*. New York: Longman.

Busick, T. (2013). Effect of reading intervention strategies for elementary students at-risk of reading disabilities. [https://www.nmu.edu/education/sites/Drupal Education/files userfiles/Busick-Traci-MR.pdf](https://www.nmu.edu/education/sites/Drupal%20Education/files/userfiles/Busick-Traci-MR.pdf).

Caillies, M. (2018). Parental reading involvement in the Philippines: A review of literature. *International Journal of Early Childhood Education Care*. ISSN. 2289-3156/eISSN 2550-1763. Vol. 6, 42-50.

Cain, D., Catada, K., & Mascardo, E., (2012). Parental involvement and reading comprehension skills among grade 6 pupils. Graduate Thesis, Mindanao State University –Iligan Institute of Technology.

Cambria, CM. & Phillips, B. (2019). Comprehension tools for teachers: Reading for understanding from prekindergarten through fourth grade. *Educational Psychology Review*.

Chall, JF. (2018). First-grade teachers' response to three models of professional development in reading. *Reading and Writing Journal*.

Coady, R.F. (2018). Vocabulary and reading comprehension as a measure of reading skills of Filipino children. <http://www.academia.org>. *vocabulary-and-reading-comprehension-as-a-measure-of-reading-skills*.

Cook, CM. (2019). Individualizing teaching in beginning reading. *Better: Evidence-based Education*, Autumn. 2014:4–7.

Cummins, M. M. (2020). Parental Involvement in relation to students' reading performance. *Globusjournal of progressive education a*

refereed research journal,94.

Cunningham, S., & Stanovich, I. (2019). Parents' attitudes and behavior, the learning environment, and their influence on children's early reading achievement. *Open Journal of Modern Linguistics*.

D.E. (1980). Schemata: The building blocks of cognition. In: R.J. Spiro et al. (eds) *Theoretical Issues in Reading Comprehension*. Lawrence Erlbaum.

Dave, V. (2018). Parent involvement and literacy achievement. *Education 703*.Spring. <https://slideplayer.com/slide/6898211/>.

Davis, A.P. (2018). Authentic assessment of modular distance learning in reading. *Journal Publication*.

De Gracia, A.O., Apitac, L.E., Candilado, M.A., Dimampaso, & R.C. Balbadong, R.M. (2018). The level of reading comprehension in English of the grade four pupils of Iligan City Central School. Unpublished Undergraduate thesis. Iligan Capitol College, Iligan City.

De leon, P. M., Eccles, J. S., & Linver, M. (2018). Girls do well in math, and better in reading. Paper presented at the Biennial Meeting of the Society for Research on Adolescence.

Deffer, J. (1960). Cultural-cognitive issues in academic achievement: Toward an understanding of cross-national differences. <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/read/10322/chapter/6#124>.

Dingco, J., & Sumile, M. (2012). Reading comprehension skills among the fourth-year secondary students of Mindanao State University Maigo School of Arts and Trades. Undergraduate Thesis, Mindanao State University Maigo School of Arts and Trades, Maigo, Lanao del Norte.

Dwight, S. (2019). The impact of parent involvement on reading comprehension test scores of fourth-grade. Goucher College.

Ebisa, E. (2006). Reading predictors and their relationship to the reading ability of grade four pupils at Dona Juana Actub Lluh Memorial Central School: The basis for an intervention program. Unpublished Theses.

Elders, J. (2019). Explicit comprehension instruction: A review of research and a new conceptualization of instruction. *The Elementary School Journal*. University of Chicago Press.

Gersten, E. (2018). Parent involvement: Increasing student literacy skills and values. *Education 7201: Seminar in Applied Theory and Research 1*. <https://slideplayer.com/slide/7297403/>.

Gillaco, M. (2019). Level of word recognition and reading comprehension: A basis for a reading program. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts, and Sciences*.

Hansen, T. (2018). Theory of reading comprehension. www.domain.edu.

Harris, A. (2019). How to increase reading ability. New York, Longmans: Green and Company.

Harmon, H. (2019). Individualized reading in first grade. *Educational Leadership*, vol. 16.

Hausheer, R., Hanseen A., & Dumas, D.M. (2018). Improving reading fluency and comprehension among elementary students' evaluation of a school remedial reading program. Baise State University. [HTTPhttp://,SC.Montana.edu/article/v9n9.pdf](http://SC.Montana.edu/article/v9n9.pdf).

Hernandez, A. (2019). Reading comprehension problems, causes, symptoms, and support. eprints.uny.ac.id/.

Hirsch, J., & Andrews, S. (2018). Lexical quality and reading skill: Bottom-up and top-down contributions to sentence processing. *Scientific Studies of Reading*.

Howard, A. (2011). Supporting young children's literacy learning through home-school partnerships: The effectiveness of a home repeated-reading intervention. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 307-333.

Hymes, A. P. (2018). Teaching reading and writing: A guidebook for tutoring and remediating students. Estofer Road, Plymouth: Rowman & Littlefield Education.

Jala, G.T. (2020). Pupils' reading comprehension, problem-solving skills, and academic performance. *Journal of World English and Educational Practices (JWEEP): Volume 2 No (2020)*.

Jenkins, M. (2019). The main purpose of reading is comprehension. Volume 2: Executive summary.

Klezien, A., & Trong, K. (2019). Influence of the home literacy environment on reading motivation and reading comprehension. *Journal of World Educational Practices (JWEP): Volume 5 No (2020)*.

Kuhara-Kojima, J.K. & Vaughn, S. (2018). Promoting reading comprehension, content learning, and English acquisition through collaborative strategic reading (CSR). *The Reading Teacher*, 52, 738-747.

Larayos, H.Y., & Malawani, N.A. (2019). Cognitive skills and reading comprehension of grade four pupils in Sergeant Miguel Canoy

- Memorial Elementary School: Basis for an action plan. Unpublished Undergraduate Thesis, Mindanao State University Iligan Institute of Technology, Iligan City.
- Lenski, M., & Lewis, K. (2018). Literacy of reading difficulties. Seattle University. [Researchgate.net/publication/234746923](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234746923).
- Lesgold, H. B., & Perfetti, L. (2018). Preventing reading failure: Phonological awareness assessment and instruction. *Preventing School Failure*.
- Lories, L., Routes, Y. & Stahl, M. (2018). Teaching reading comprehension to enhance understanding. *Journal Publication*.
- Lubliner, A., & Smetana, J. (2019). The condition of education in brief (NCES 2003-068). Washington, DC: U
- Manalo, M.K. (2018). Literacy courses and the prevention of reading difficulties. Elon University. [Researchgate.net/publication/234746923](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234746923).
- Manzo, P., Hook, P. E., & McCabe, R. (2019). The efficacy of computer-based supplement phonics programs for advancing reading skills elementary students. http://www.lexiauk.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/efficacy_study.pdf.
- Mare, P. (2020). Teachers' attitude as a correlate of students' academic performance. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*.
- May, C., Miao, Y. & Shippen, P. (2019). A reading model for involving parents of children with learning and behavior problems in the schools. *Journal Publication*.
- McNamara, H. (2019). Fluency in education place. <https://www.eduplace.com>.
- Meissner, L. & Stahl, M. (2018). Strategies that work teaching comprehension to enhance understanding. Stenhouse.
- Mezynski, C. (2018). Reading text. *Classroom. TESOL Quarterly*,34/3, 585-589. www.google.com.
- Middleton, M.E. (2019). Reading motivation and reading comprehension. Master of Education. The Ohio State University.
- Mullis, D.R., Chard, D.J., & Pool, J.L. (2019). A family strengths approach to early language and reading development. *Early Childhood Education*.
- Nash, W., Wickstron, K., & Snowling, K. (2018). Effect of a combined repeatedreading and questions generation intervention reading achievement. <http://www.google.com>.
- Nelson, M. (2018). Effect of parental involvement on the reading skills of pupils in Ondo Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Social Policy*. Vol. 7 No. 4, December 2020.
- Nilep, V. (2019). Exploring rhymes and song strategies in improving spoken English language skills among lower primary school pupils. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*; Vol. 10 Issue 2 series 3, Pp. 5 – 10.
- Oakhil, E. (2019). Assessing the reading habits of future classroom teachers in the context of their socio-demographic features. *International Journal of Behavioral Cognitive, Educational, and Psychological Sciences*.
- Paul, K., & Elders, P. (2019). The effect of teachers' attitudes and teacher efficacy for inclusive education on emotional distress in primary school teachers in Japan. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fedu.2020.570988>.
- Phil-IRI Report. (2023). Department of Education Order No. 45, s. 2002. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2002/09/11/do-45-s-2002-reading-literacy-program-in-the-elementary-schools/>.
- Piaget, J. (1968). Cognitive development. <http://www.learningandteaching.info/learning/piaget.htm>.
- Plocher, E. & Paris, M. (2019). Introduction to research in education,7th Ed. Belmont, CA: Thomson & I Wadsworth Research /oc/c/318408193.
- Prabuh, M. (2019). The effectiveness of the dimensional approach in teaching reading among grade VI pupils. *Journal Publication*.
- Rand Reading Study Group. (2002). Reading for understanding: Toward a research and development program in reading comprehension. Santa Monica, CA: Office of Education Research and Improvement.
- Richek, C., & Vandevier, M. (2018). Workbook in English 6. Reverse the education crisis.
- Rupley, W.H., Blair, T.R. & William, W.D. (2019). Effective reading instruction for struggling readers: The role of direct/explicit teaching, reading & writing. *Quarterly*, link to this article.
- Salinger, P., & Fleischman J. (2019). Grade- level invariance of a theoretical causal structure predicting reading comprehension with vocabulary and oral reading fluency. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 24 (3).

- Samonte, T. (2018). Reading comprehension performance of grade IV pupils as influenced by their home reading support, attributes, and attitudes towards learning. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Misamis University.
- Saracho, Olivia N. (2007). Hispanic families as facilitators of their children's literacy development. *Journal of Hispanic Higher Education*. <http://studysites.sagepub.com/kgrantstudy/articles/14/Saracho.pdf>.
- Schatschneider, M., Leeuwe, J. & Staporage, V. (2018). Socio-cultural variation in reading comprehension development among fifth graders in Peru. Springer. Spring Science Business Media.
- Sheehan, H. (20118). Improving skills through effective reading strategies. 709-714.
- Stahl, L. (2019). The effect of meta-cognitive learning strategies on English learning. <https://search.proquest.com/doc view>.
- Stanovich, F. (2019). A short analysis of the nature of reading. *English Language Teaching Journal*, Vol. 3 No. 3, 341-351.
- Stephen, N. (2019). Effective mathematics intervention programs for students in Grades Three through Five. <https://www.education/sites/Education/Files>.
- Tabors, H., Snow, C.E., Dickenson, M.S., & Griffin, P. (Eds.). (2018). Preventing reading difficulties in young children. National Academy Press.
- Tankersley, M. (2018). Reading comprehension ability of grade VI pupils of Kinangay Sur Elementary. <http://world conference.net/proceedings/gse>.
- Vacca, Y., Vacca (2019). Importance of reading skills. <https://nccur.lib.nccu.edu.w/bitstream>.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Esnaira D. Tamburac

Department of Education – Philippines

Carlito A. Abarquez, PhD

St. Peter's College – Philippines